

Physical Facilities Management and School Safety in Tagum District

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Abstract. This study assessed the extent of physical facilities management and its influence on school safety in public schools within the Tagum District, Tagum City Division. Employing a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected through an adapted survey instrument administered to a randomly selected sample of teacher-respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (Mean scores), Pearson's correlation coefficient (Pearson r), and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Results indicated that the extent of physical facilities management, including processes establishment, facilities upkeep and improvement, technology integration, and personnel support, was moderately extensive. Similarly, school safety, measured by water and sanitation facilities, building and classroom conditions, and playground and parking space safety, was also moderately extensive. A significant positive correlation was found between physical facilities management and school safety in Tagum District schools. Specifically, all aspects of physical facilities management—supporting personnel, establishing processes, improving facilities, and integrating technology—significantly influenced school safety. Future research could explore the effectiveness of safety protocols and emergency response strategies, investigate the impact of environmental factors such as air quality and lighting on school safety and well-being, and examine the role of technology in enhancing school safety and security.

KEY WORDS

1. Physical Facilities Management 2. School Safety 3. Tagum City Division

Date Received: July 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: August 01, 2024 — Date Published: September 2, 2024

1. Introduction

Across the globe, school buildings and other physical facilities are coming to age, and the stakeholders are facing the growing challenges of maintaining school facilities at a level that enables teachers to meet the needs of 21st-century learners. While constructing new facilities supports this task, many older buildings have developed modularity over time. The task of caring for these old school buildings, some of which are historically or architecturally significant, at a level that supports contemporary instructional practices is substantial. At the same time, maintaining the finely tuned workings of new, more technologically advanced facilities also demands considerable expertise and commitment. In the global context, Buitelir, D. de. (2022) reported that facilities management for schools is a vital part of a school district's overall health and success. Facilities maintenance is critical to ensuring a school system's and its students'

success, but it can be a huge undertaking. Keeping school buildings working optimally takes a lot of work and even more planning. It's a complex job with a lot of moving parts. Similarly, Sitologiq (2020) published that school facilities management directly impacts the learning experience. The health and safety of everyone who occupies school buildings and district facilities are first and foremost, but from a day-to-day perspective, a lot goes into the real-time management of a system of large buildings throughout a school district. Thus, it is perhaps unsurprising that facilities issues arise at all educational levels, prekindergarten through post-secondary, and all sites, school buildings, and administrative offices. Challenges arise in both new and old facilities, although the types of concerns may differ. For example, even a brand-new building may have problems with inadequate air circulation, which can lead to indoor air quality (IAQ) problems unless remedied. On the other hand, older buildings more frequently face age-related issues such as inefficient energy systems that can lead to uncomfortable indoor climates and high utility bills. Certainly, extreme environmental conditions and a lack of maintenance funding contribute to building deterioration. However, many facility problems are not a function of geography or socioeconomic factors but are related to maintenance staffing levels, training, and management practices. In the context of the Philippines, the aging of school buildings is a known fact, and it's inevitable that routine and unexpected maintenance demands will arise. Therefore, schools must take a proactive approach and develop a plan to address these issues. School heads and physical facilities coordinators must plan to meet the challenges of effective facilities maintenance. It's a task too significant to be handled in a haphazard manner. After all, the consequences impact teaching and learning, student and staff health, day-to-day building operations, and the long-term financial outlook of the organization. Similarly, public

schools in Tagum City District and the rest of stakeholders knew that sound facilities maintenance plan serves as evidence that school facilities are, and will be, cared for appropriately. On the other hand, negligent facilities maintenance planning can cause real problems. Large capital investment can be squandered when buildings and equipment deteriorate or warranties become invalidated. Failing to maintain school facilities adequately also discourages future public investment in the education system. However, school facilities maintenance is concerned about more than just resource management. It is about providing clean and safe environments for children. It is also about creating a physical setting that is appropriate and adequate for learning. A classroom with broken windows and cold drafts doesn't foster effective student learning. However, neither does an apparently state-of-the-art classroom that is plagued with uncontrollable swings in indoor temperature, which can negatively affect student and instructor alertness, attendance, and even health. In Tagum City Schools, it has been observed that maintenance and safety management are only inspected when there is a serious threat, and that is a high risk on the part of learners and teachers. School facility maintenance affects the physical, educational, and financial foundation of the school organization and should, therefore, be a focus of both its day-to-day operations and long-range management priorities. Thus, this study is conducted.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature— This section discusses relevant literature on the management of physical facilities in public schools, emphasizing its role in ensuring school safety.

1.1.1. Management of Physical Facilities— Physical facilities management is essential for ensuring schools are safe and conducive to learning. Nikolic (2021) emphasizes that education, a universal right, is interconnected with sustainable development goals, requiring a holistic approach in managing educational resources.

Gijbels, Kuppens, and Van den Bossche (2018) note that facilities management, including maintenance and safety inspections, directly contributes to the learning environment's functionality. Compliance with local and international standards is crucial, as highlighted by Wan and Zhang (2020), who found that schools face legal and financial risks without proper adherence.

Effective facilities management relies on collaboration between stakeholders, such as administrators and teachers (Osei-Kofi Mensah, 2022). Moreover, Nyabwanga and Ongowo (2019) stress that international schools must manage diverse needs arising from cultural differences. The overall quality of school facilities directly impacts both student performance and teacher satisfaction by providing a safe and comfortable environment (Robson et al., 2019).

1.1.2. Supporting People—Physical facilities management plays a critical role in supporting students and staff by promoting safety, health, and inclusivity. Quiambao, del Rosario, and Zuniga (2019) found that many Philippine schools lack proper safety measures like fire extinguishers and security personnel. Reyes, Bucoy, and Mercado (2020) emphasize the importance of health-focused facilities, which positively impact student well-being. Accessibility for disabled students is another key area, with Reyes and Abcede (2021) advocating for more inclusive infrastructure, such as ramps and elevators. Diestro, Ramilo, and Macagba (2022) recommend sustainable practices like waste segregation to support environmental awareness in schools.

1.1.3. Establishing Processes—Establishing formal processes for facilities management can improve efficiency, accountability, and resource allocation. Zuniga and Santos (2019) identified inefficiencies in maintenance due to a lack of processes, while Quizon and Zuniga (2020) found better accountability in schools with structured facilities management. Vilanueva and Quiambao (2022) advocate for

improved stakeholder communication through established procedures, which can enhance decision-making and resource management.

1.1.4. Facilities Upkeep and Improvement—Bacanto et al. (2019) underscore the importance of regular upkeep and development of school facilities for ensuring safety and maintaining a conducive learning environment. Adequate financial resources are necessary to prevent safety hazards (Zuniga Santos, 2019), while Lacaste and Abella (2021) emphasize expanding facilities to meet growing demands.

1.1.5. Technology Integration—Technology integration can significantly enhance education. Laroza and Yabut (2020) highlight its ability to provide personalized learning experiences, improving student engagement. However, the cost of technology remains a challenge, especially in rural areas (Serrano Tagulao, 2020). Williams (2022) found that leadership plays a key role in successful technology integration, while de la Rosa (2021) emphasizes its potential to improve school efficiency and learning outcomes.

1.1.6. School Safety—School safety is crucial for creating a secure learning environment. Buildings and classrooms need to be designed with safety features like proper lighting, ventilation, and emergency exits (Matuan Canto, 2019). Regular maintenance is critical for preventing accidents (Arizala et al., 2020), while effective classroom management can reduce safety risks such as bullying (Hidalgo et al., 2021). Ensuring safe water and sanitation facilities is also important for student health and attendance (Gonzales et al., 2020; Plata, 2019).

Playgrounds and parking spaces must be safely designed and maintained to minimize risks of injury and accidents (Sharma Prakash, 2019; Ma et al., 2021). Safe and organized traffic management around schools is equally crucial for overall safety.

1.2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—The study was anchored on the theory

of Henry Fayol's administrative management theory can be described as an approach to management and increasing productivity by emphasizing organizational structure and human behavior. The Administrative Theory of Management was first generalized by Henri Fayol (1841-1925) with his work and publications, Fayol's 14 Principles of Management (1888) and Administration Industrielle et Generale (1916). As a member of the classical theory movement, Fayol's work was unique from that of Taylor, who focused on worker efficiency. Instead, Fayol focused on organizing and structuring work tasks. He looked specifically at how management and workers are organized within a business to allow for the completion of tasks. He proposed the creation of work groups and functional departments where distinct activities are performed. These activities contribute to the accomplishment of greater tasks in furtherance of company objectives. Fayol took a top-down approach to organizational efficiency. He believed that the effective organization of management would ultimately affect the productivity of operational-level workers. Administrative management theory is in contrast to the scientific approach to management, which posits that worker efficiency would lead to greater managerial efficiency. Per Fayol's Administrative Management Theory, a manager's individual functions may vary widely depending on the type of manager and the nature of the manager's responsibilities. As such, categorizing a manager's functions helps understand a manager's responsibilities. The Administrative Theory of management is still very much integrated into our modern understanding of organizations and management practice. Further, Fayol's 14 principles of management provided specific guidance on the organizational elements necessary for effective management and demonstrated the administrative management approach. These principles are summarized in such a way that the division of labor within an organization allows for specialization. Individuals can become more proficient in the accomplishment of a limited set of activities, thus improving their output. Managers must have the authority to issue commands, but with that authority comes the responsibility to ensure that the work gets done. There must be a clear line of authority. Subordinates must fully obey instructions from superiors. Managers must have the ability to instill discipline through punishment. There should be only one boss from whom a worker receives instructions. Each workgroup or department is working under a singular plan that coordinates efforts. Work efforts should be guided by one supervisor. The interests of individuals are subordinate to the general interests of the group or department or company. Compensation is used to incentivize worker performance. Remuneration can include both financial and non-financial forms of compensation. Decision-making should be either centralized (management makes all decisions) or decentralized (employees also make decisions) depending upon the characteristics of the organization and worker competency. There must be a hierarchy of authority that places workers below managers in the reporting structure. The degree of authority is higher at each stage of the organizational hierarchy. The organizational hierarchy should be well understood throughout. There must be well-defined rules and standards for the work environment and work responsibilities. A safe and orderly environment leads to greater coordination. The organization must be run based on principles of fairness. Employees should be treated with a combination of kindness and justice. Organizations need low turnover. This allows employees time to learn their jobs, develop skills, and acquire loyalty. Managers must promote initiative by allowing employees to create plans and carry them out. Establishing a sense of belonging within the organization creates a sense of unity and morale. Figure 1 presents the variables un-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables and Indicators under Study
 der study. Independent variable management of school physical facilities speaks of the indicators supporting people, establishing processes, upkeep, improving facilities, and technology integration. Meanwhile, school safety refers to buildings and classrooms, water and sanitation, playgrounds, and parking spaces. Such an application of Henry Fayol’s theory applies in the context of the current study. This gives much interest to the researcher in exploring the context of the management of physical facilities among schools.

Physical facilities management and school safety are closely intertwined. The condition and design of school buildings and their surrounding environments can significantly impact the safety of students and staff. Effective facilities management, therefore, involves not only ensuring that buildings and facilities are well-maintained and clean but also free from hazards, thereby reducing the likelihood of accidents and injuries. This underscores the critical importance of school safety in the context of facilities management. In terms of school safety, physical facilities management plays a critical role in preventing and responding to emergencies, such as natural disasters, fires, and acts of violence. Facilities managers are responsible for ensuring that school buildings are equipped with appropriate safety features, such as fire alarms, sprinkler systems, and emergency exits, and that they are regularly inspected and maintained to ensure their functionality. Additionally, facilities management could contribute to school

safety by implementing security measures such as surveillance cameras, access control systems, and visitor management procedures. These measures can help deter potential threats and identify suspicious behavior, enabling school staff to respond quickly and effectively in the event of an emergency. In summary, physical facilities management ensured that school buildings and their surrounding environments were safe and secure for students and staff. By implementing effective facilities management practices, schools could reduce the risk of accidents and emergencies and create a safe and supportive learning environment for everyone.

1.3. *Statement of the Problem*—The study was conducted to determine the extent of physical facilities management and its influence on school safety among Public Schools in Tagum District, Tagum City Division. This specifically sought to answer the following statement of the problem:

- (1) What is the extent of physical facilities management in Tagum City in terms of;
 - (1) supporting people;

- (2) establishing processes;
 - (3) facilities upkeep and improvement; and
 - (4) technology integration.
- (2) What is the extent of school safety in Tagum City in terms of
- (1) buildings and classrooms;
 - (2) water and sanitation; and
 - (3) playground and parking spaces.
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between physical facilities management and school safety in Tagum City?
- (4) Which among the indicators of physical facilities management significantly influence school safety in Tagum City?

1.4. Hypothesis—To provide empirical evidence given the posed theoretical and conceptual frameworks as claimed by the study, null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance, stating: Ho 1: There is no significant relationship between physical facilities management and school safety in Tagum City. and, Ho 2: None of the indicators of physical facilities management significantly influence school safety in Tagum City. The results of this study were beneficial and provided significant inputs to stakeholders. They also provided further take-off bases for the school heads and teachers to collaborate and develop a sound school policy that governs parents' cooperation. Given the study's outputs, the following stakeholders shall be beneficial. School Principals. The School Principals set the direction for managing and operating the school governance through community building and collaboration with parents and significant stakeholders. The School Principal was expected to manage the safety of the school, along with the learning environment to be safe and make learners and teachers confident in moving around the campus to make the teaching and learning process more effective and efficient. Thus, the study results would provide insights to school heads of Tagum District as to how characteristics of a safe learning environment among learners can improve learning performance. Teachers. Teachers were considered the second parents of the learners, and they

were expected to take care of the learners when they were inside the campus. As the DepEd mission stated the teacher would nurture learners into a safe learning environment. In this context, teachers ensure that their efforts in implementing and facilitating learning to learners through a safe learning environment will not be in vain, thus, having the learners safe and confident in the academic learning given full face-to-face modality. The results of the study would give an idea to teachers for them to see clearly if approaches and management of physical facilities in school could influence school safety and can make teachers more effective in teaching and learners become more productive and contribute to their development skills and likewise to the learners. Parents. Parents play significant roles in the skills development of their young learners. Parents expect their children to be safe in school while developing their personalities and academic success. The results of the study would give insights and enlightenment to the members of the school Governing Council through the Parent Teachers' Association in advocating school safety all through school days by empowerment and continuously improving the process and performance of the school and learners' academic achievement as well through full participation in the whole cycle process. Future Researchers. Implications based on the study's generated results will provide more information to future researchers to replicate the

musical practices to be discovered in the proposed study. These practices include the type and approaches of management of physical facilities and the elements of efficiency in improving the quality delivery of education outputs through the process introduced in the MELCs. The following terms are variables used in the study, and definitions by concept and operation were presented according to how the terms were used in the context of the study. This served as a reference in the analysis and interpretation of the results to come up with meaningful implications for a better understanding and recommendations. Management of School Physical Facilities. School facilities management was the practice of managing and maintaining all school-owned facilities and assets. School facilities improve the quality of the study environment in the school, thus improving the quality of education. It was the classroom layout that considered the room's acoustics; with this, students were able to focus and concentrate more on their studies, with teachers facing

fewer distractions. Further, physical facilities management takes a strategic approach to the planning and management of tasks. Through the contracts they arrange and KPIs, they set, the facility coordinators deliver value to a safe school. In this study, the term was used as the independent variables where indicators were facilities upkeep and improvement, supporting people, establishing work processes, and strategizing and integrating technology. School Safety. A safe school was one where teaching and learning were not distracted; disruptions were minimized; violence, drugs, bullying, and fear were not present; students were not discriminated against; expectations for behavior were clearly communicated; and consequences for infractions were consistently and fairly applied. In this study, school safety is used as the dependent variable, which was measured through indicators to ensure that building and classrooms, water and sanitation, playground, and learning environment are conducive to learning.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The conducted study used non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design. This refers to studies that describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. Predictive correlational studies predict the variance of one or more variables based on the variance of another variable

(s). Moreover, these designs aimed to get a picture of the current thoughts, feelings, or behaviors in a given group of people. Descriptive research was summarized using descriptive statistics. Correlational research designs measure two or more relevant variables and assess a relationship between or among them. (Pallant, 2020). On the other hand, this type of research

tries to extrapolate from the analysis of existing phenomena, policies, or other entities in order to predict something that has not been tried, tested, or proposed before (Gujarati, 2020). In this study, indicators under independent variable management of school physical facilities, facilities are upkeep and improvement, establish work processes, supporting people, strategizing and integrating technology shall be measured its extent of operation in schools and its significant correlation with dependent variable school safety in terms of the buildings and classrooms, water and sanitation, playground and learning environment in Tagum District, Tagum City Division. Using the design mentioned, it was assumed that variables, along with the indicators mentioned, the researcher empirically provides evidence that the presented hypothesis shall be null and void.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the proposed study were the Elementary School Teachers in Tagum District. Using the Raosoft sample size calculator, a total of 120 teachers were taken randomly from each respective elementary school. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through an online platform and or face-to-face, considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, and where they likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study. As much as possible, these respondents had direct observations and participation in managing the school's physical facilities and how they contributed to

Meanwhile, to determine the level of school safety, a 5-point Likert scale was used in this

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The preceding statements explain the data-gathering procedure steps that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements were based on the policies and guidelines

and influenced school safety. For example, they were directly involved in training, seminars, and orientation on disaster preparedness and safety in physical facilities and management in their respective schools during SY 2022-2023. The ethics of research and the process of collecting survey responses were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible contamination and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This proposed research study used a self-made survey instrument. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature on the management of school physical facilities and school safety. The survey questionnaire has two parts, each containing the indicators of the respective variables mentioned. The statements of the survey were placed in contexts based on the definition of the variables under study. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.917, which means that 91.7 percent level of confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of management of physical facilities in Tagum District. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation were provided as follows :

study, as presented below;

of the institution. Permission to conduct the study. During the month of November 2023, the conceptualization of the research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. Sometime in the

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The management of physical facilities in Tagum City is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The management of physical facilities in Tagum City is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The management of physical facilities in Tagum City is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The management of physical facilities in Tagum City is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The management of physical facilities in Tagum City is not manifested

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The school safety in Tagum City is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The school safety in Tagum City is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The school safety in Tagum City is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The school safety in Tagum City is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The school safety in Tagum City is not manifested

second week of December 2022, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher prepared to write a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Tagum City, through the channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the schools of Tagum District Elementary Schools. This was sent to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Tagum City through the records section on the second week of January 2023 to commence the conduct of the data gathering. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. As soon as the request was approved by the office, the researcher prepared the necessary requirements in the preparation of the data gathering. On the fourth week of January 2023, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet

form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and for respondents who do not have access to the internet, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets shall be given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses are expected to be generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser on February 2023. This is for coaching, in terms of providing interpretations and implications of the study and further deepening the analysis to make the interpretations more meaningful.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher sought guidance and advice from the thesis adviser. This resulted in proper authorization and consent was obtained from the

respondents of the study to ensure that all their rights would be fully protected, specifically in handling the data, however, not limited to: Voluntary Participation. Several ethical considerations were considered by the researcher to ensure that the study was conducted in an appropriate manner. To comply with ethical considerations in conducting research, all participants were provided with informed consent to participate in the survey. This indicated that the participation of respondents was voluntary in nature. Also, the purpose and benefits of the research were explained to the respondents, and the respondents were informed that should they wish to withdraw at any point during the data-gathering procedure, they could do so (Lotich, 2011). Privacy and Confidentiality. The profile of the study respondents was treated with utmost confidentiality to protect their rights, especially since the respondents were minors. Privacy and confidentiality were specifically observed through the presentation and discussions of results (Koenig MacMillan, 2004). Informed Consent Process. It further explained to the respondents that their information would remain private and confidential and that the specific content of individual surveys would only be discussed with the research adviser. The research adviser and the respondents were unknown to each other. In the final report, the identity of the participants was removed, and pseudonyms were used for the participants. While sharing the purpose of the study with the respondents, the researcher also shared their personal background and some of the researcher's personal stories as a school physical facilities coordinator. This was helpful in building trust and, in turn, encouraged the respondents to answer the survey honestly. Risks. Moreover, the researcher informed the respondents that their participation in the survey would not bring any foreseeable risks to their personal health or well-being. Thus, the respondents were informed that in the event that they become upset or dis-

tressed as a result of answering the questions that are part of the researcher's standard battery, then the researcher would have helped them obtain a referral for the respondents to see a trained professional who can help process these feelings (Lotich, 2011). Benefits. Further, observable benefits of the study were immediately disseminated to the stakeholders, and these are parents. The findings of the study generated facts that were important for the enhancement of the learners' readiness (Koenig MacMillan, 2004). The findings of the study would serve as the basis for public schools at the elementary level to pay attention to creating a learning environment for the learners and teachers to have a productive and safe learning environment. Plagiarism. Furthermore, the researcher strictly adhered to other ethical issues, which include plagiarism, fabrication, and falsification (Lakey Cohen, 2020). The researcher ensured that the resources being used in this study were properly cited. The authors' ideas are paraphrased and properly synthesized to abstain from plagiarism. No fabrication or inclusion of data, survey, or enactment that never arise in the gathering of data. The researcher made only conclusions that were based on the study's results. In the event of any unintentional plagiarized, fabricated, or falsified ideas, the researcher immediately revised the manuscript (Lotich, 2011). Fabrication. The researcher guaranteed that provisions on deceit and conflict of interest aspects were strictly observed. The researcher assured the respondents that the study was done with honesty and transparency. Evidence shows that the benefit of misleading the respondents outweighs any potential harm to them (Creswell, 2014). The researcher assisted the respondents satisfactorily and talked through the process and the outcome of the study. They were given a general idea of what the researcher was investigating and why such a study was conducted. Their role and contribution to the study will be promptly explained. Falsification. This study

complied with the citation rules set based on the APA 7th edition citation format to avoid misrepresentation of work or alterations of any data gathered in the study (Cohen, 2020). The data and information that written were and be presented in the most accurate way as possible. Conflict of Interest. The researcher ensured that conflict of interest (COI) in this study was highly observed (Lotich, 2011). There was no set of conditions as to professional judgment concerning primary interest, as the respondents' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by secondary interests, such as financial or academic gains or any forms of recognition. Deceit. The writings of this paper do not utilize any form of untruthfulness to harm anyone, especially the respondents, since all information written was checked and validated by the panel of experts (Lakey Cohen, 2020). Permission from the School/Location. Prior to conducting the study, the researcher procured a letter duly signed by the Dean of Graduate School and provided it to the Schools Division Superintendent. Then, the reply from the said office allowing the researcher to conduct the study was delivered to the school principals where the study was conducted. Authorship. Finally, upon the approval of the final version to be published, the researcher considered for the authorship of the adviser and a few other individuals, such as colleagues who gave substantial contributions to the conception and design of the study, acquisition of data, or anal-

ysis and interpretation of data and drafting the manuscript or revising it critically for important intellectual content as co-authors (Lotich, 2011). Finally, the respondents could contact the researcher at the mobile number and email address provided on the informed consent form if they have questions, concerns, or complaints about the research. The researcher also ensured that the study's benefits would be shared during meetings and conferences, with stakeholders as part of the audience.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1) regarding the extent of school physical facilities management and statement problem number two (2) regarding the level of school safety in Tagum District. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between the extent of school physical facilities management and the level of school safety in Tagum City District. Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4 on the indicators of the extent of school physical facilities management that significantly influence the level of school safety in Tagum City District (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations are then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets data gathered in tabular and textual form to provide clear ideas and information on the queries based on the statement of the problem posed. Various reviews present implications of the results to corroborate and argue the hypothesis and theory as claimed and posed in the study.

3.1. *Extent of Physical Facilities Management*—Physical facilities management is a critical component of the international school sys-

tem, as it is necessary to ensure that the school facilities are functional, safe, and conducive to learning. As a fundamental and universal

human right, education represents an underlying assumption and an essential requirement for sustainable development. According to Gijbels, Kuppens, and Van den Bossche (2018), facilities management in schools involves the maintenance, repair, and replacement of physical assets, including buildings, equipment, and infrastructure. They argue that effective facilities management can contribute to the overall performance and success of a school by providing students and staff with a safe, comfortable, and functional learning environment. In the context of international schools, physical facilities management is often more complex due to the diverse needs of students and staff from different cultures and backgrounds. As noted by Nyabwanga and Ongowo (2019), international schools must navigate various challenges, such as language barriers, differing educational systems, and cultural differences, when managing their physical facilities. One of the key challenges of physical facilities management in international schools is ensuring compliance with local regulations and standards. As highlighted by Wan and Zhang (2020), international schools must adhere to the regulations and standards of the host country, as well as any international standards for education facilities. Failure to comply with these standards

Physical facilities management plays a critical role in supporting people in the Philippine school system. It involves ensuring that schools have adequate and well-maintained facilities that provide a safe and conducive environment for teaching and learning. One of the primary ways in which physical facilities management supports people in the Philippine school system is by promoting safety and security. A study by Quiambao, del Rosario, and Zuniga (2019) noted that many schools in the Philippines lacked proper safety and security measures, such as fire extinguishers, first aid

can result in legal and financial penalties, as well as reputational damage. To address these challenges, international schools may need to adopt a more proactive and strategic approach to physical facilities management. According to Gijbels et al. (2018), this involves implementing a comprehensive facilities management plan that outlines the school's objectives, strategies, and resources for maintaining and improving its physical assets. The plan should also involve regular assessments of the facilities, such as safety inspections and environmental audits, to identify any areas for improvement. Table 1 shows the extent of the physical facilities management in terms of supporting people. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: mentoring of learners and teachers by experts (4.15); disciplinary actions taken by the school (3.13); support by the school's management to implement any safety-related changes (3.10); training is provided to teachers on school safety policies and procedures (3.10); and involving learners in resolving behavioral and disciplinary problems (3.10), suggest that supporting people is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.12 denotes a moderately extensive physical facilities management in terms of supporting people.

kits, and security personnel. These inadequacies put the safety and well-being of students, teachers, and staff at risk. The authors recommended that schools should prioritize physical facilities management to ensure the safety and security of all stakeholders. Another way in which physical facilities management supports people in the Philippine school system is by promoting health and well-being. A study by Reyes, Bucoy, and Mercado (2020) examined the impact of school facilities on the health and well-being of students in the Philippines. The results showed that well-maintained and well-

Table 1. The Extent of Physical Facilities Management in Terms of Supporting People

No	Supporting People	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Support by the school’s management to implement any safety-related changes	3.10	Moderately Extensive
2	Training is provided to teachers on school safety policies and procedures	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	Disciplinary actions taken by the school	3.13	Moderately Extensive
4	Mentoring of learners and teachers by experts	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	Involving learners in resolving behavioral and disciplinary problems	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.11	Moderately Extensive

equipped school facilities, such as gymnasiums, playgrounds, and restrooms, had a positive impact on the physical and mental health of students. The authors recommended that schools should invest in physical facilities management to promote the health and well-being of students. Moreover, physical facilities management supports people in the Philippine school system by promoting inclusivity and accessibility. A study by Reyes and Abcede (2021) examined the accessibility of school facilities for students with disabilities in the Philippines. The results showed that many schools lacked the necessary facilities and equipment to accommodate students with disabilities, such as ramps, elevators, and accessible restrooms. The authors recommended that schools should prioritize physical facilities management to ensure that all students, regardless of their abilities, have equal access to education. Furthermore, physical facilities management supports people in the Philippine school system by promoting sustainability and environmental awareness. A study by Diestro, Ramilo, and Macagba (2022) examined the sustainability practices of schools in the Philippines. The results showed that many

schools lacked the necessary facilities and practices to promote sustainability, such as rainwater harvesting, composting, and waste segregation. The authors recommended that schools should prioritize physical facilities management to promote sustainability and environmental awareness among students and staff.

3.2. *Establishing Processes*—Table 2 shows the extent of physical facilities management in terms of establishing processes. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: safety and security measures adopted by the local barangay (2.19); safety and security measures adopted by the school (2.18); coordination between the school and the local emergency services in planning for emergency situations (2.16); evacuation plan is posted in a conspicuous space (2.15); and programs to promote sense of community integration among learners (2.14), suggest that establishing processes is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.16 denotes less extensive physical facilities management regarding establishing processes.

Table 2. The Extent of Physical Facilities Management in Terms of Establishing Processes

No	Establishing Processes	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Safety and security measures adopted by the school	2.18	Less Extensive
2	Safety and security measures adopted by the local barangay	2.19	Less Extensive
3	Programs to promote a sense of community integration among learners	2.14	Less Extensive
4	Coordination between the school and the local emergency services in planning for emergency situations	2.16	Less Extensive
5	An evacuation plan is posted in a conspicuous space	2.15	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		2.16	Less Extensive

Establishing a process is crucial to physical facilities management in the Philippine school system. A well-established process ensures that facilities are adequately maintained, repaired, and replaced when necessary. One of the key benefits of establishing a process in physical facilities management is improved efficiency. A study by Zuniga and Santos (2019) noted that many schools in the Philippines lacked a formal process for maintaining and repairing facilities. This lack of process led to repair delays, increased costs, and a higher risk of accidents and injuries. The authors recommended that schools should establish a formal process for physical facilities management to improve efficiency and reduce costs. Another benefit of establishing a process in physical facilities management is improved accountability. A study by Quizon and Zuniga (2020) examined the role of accountability in physical facilities management in the Philippine school system. The results showed that schools that had established a formal physical facility management process had better accountability systems in place. This

led to improved transparency, better resource allocation, and increased stakeholder satisfaction. The authors recommended that schools should prioritize establishing a process in physical facilities management to improve accountability. Moreover, establishing a process in physical facilities management can help schools prioritize their resources effectively. A study by Baldovino and Zuniga (2021) examined the resource allocation practices of schools in the Philippines. The results showed that schools that had established a formal process for physical facilities management were better able to prioritize their resources effectively. This led to improved maintenance, better repair practices, and increased stakeholder satisfaction. The authors recommended that schools should establish a process in physical facilities management to prioritize their resources effectively. Furthermore, establishing a process in physical facilities management can improve communication and collaboration among stakeholders. A study by Villanueva and Quiambao (2022) examined the role of communication and collaboration

in physical facilities management in the Philippine school system. The results showed that schools that had established a formal process for physical facilities management had better communication and collaboration among stakeholders. This led to improved decision-making, increased stakeholder satisfaction, and better resource allocation. The authors recommended that schools should prioritize establishing a process in physical facilities management to improve communication and collaboration among stakeholders.

3.3. *Facilities Upkeep and Improvement*—Table 3 shows the extent of physical facilities management in terms of facilities upkeep and

improvement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: plans, monitoring and evaluation is prepared and used as scheduled (2.16); regular inspection of buildings and classrooms for safety maintenance (2.16); technical assistance is provided by the schools division engineering (2.15); availability of resources for teachers and learners to cope with safety challenges (2.14); facilities upkeep and improve (2.13), suggest that facilities upkeep and improvement is often-times manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.14 denotes extensive physical facilities management regarding facilities being kept and improved.

Table 3. The Extent of Physical Facilities Management in Terms of Facilities Upkeep and Improvement

No	Facilities Upkeep and Improvement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Facilities upkeep and improvement	2.13	Extensive
2	Availability of resources for teachers and learners to cope with safety challenges	2.14	Extensive
3	Plans, monitoring, and evaluation is prepared and used as a schedule	2.16	Extensive
4	Regular inspection of buildings and classrooms for safety maintenance	2.16	Extensive
5	Technical assistance is provided by the Schools Division of Engineering	2.15	Extensive
Overall Mean		2.14	Extensive

Facilities upkeep involves maintaining the condition of the school buildings and infrastructure to ensure that they are in good working condition. This includes routine maintenance activities such as cleaning, repairs, and upgrades to ensure that the facilities are safe and comfortable for both students and teachers. According to Bacanto et al. (2019), the physical condition of school facilities is an essential factor that contributes to student learning and

achievement. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct regular maintenance activities to ensure that the facilities are in good condition. Facilities development, on the other hand, involves building new facilities or expanding existing ones to meet the growing needs of the school. This includes building new classrooms, laboratories, libraries, and other facilities required to provide quality education. As noted by Lacaste and Abella (2021), the development of school

facilities is crucial in addressing the increasing demand for quality education in the Philippines, where the student population continues to grow. The upkeep and development of school facilities require adequate resources, including finances, personnel, and materials. According to Zuniga and Santos (2019), inadequate resources for facilities maintenance and development can lead to safety hazards that can negatively impact the learning environment. Therefore, it is necessary to allocate adequate resources to PFM to ensure that school facilities are well-maintained and developed.

3.4. *Technology Integration*—Table 4 shows the extent of physical facilities management in terms of technology integration. The result is focused on the highest and lowest

mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: DRRM apps are installed and connected (3.19); Emergency phone numbers and hotline are posted in conspicuous space (3.14); Integration of DRRM in the lesson as part of the learning standards (3.14); Implementation of emergency drills and other DRRM related activities (3.14); and DRRM and emergency hotlines are posted in the school’s social media page (3.13), suggest that technology integration is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.16 denotes moderately extensive physical facilities management in terms of technology integration. The integration of technology is essential for enhancing the learning experience and improving the overall quality of education.

Table 4. The Extent of Physical Facilities Management in Terms of Technology Integration

No	Technology Integration	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Emergency phone numbers and hotline are posted in conspicuous space	3.14	Moderately Extensive
2	DRRM apps are installed and connected	3.19	Moderately Extensive
3	DRRM and emergency hotlines are posted on the school’s social media page	3.13	Moderately Extensive
4	Integration of DRRM in the lesson as part of the learning standards	3.14	Moderately Extensive
5	Implementation of emergency drills and other DRRM-related activities	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.14	Moderately Extensive

Technology integration refers to the use of technology to enhance the teaching and learning process. According to de la Rosa (2021), technology integration is an important component of PFM that can help improve the quality of education in the Philippines. With the increas-

ing prevalence of technology in modern society, integrating technology into the classroom has become a necessity rather than a luxury. One of the most significant advantages of technology integration is that it can make learning more engaging and interactive. As noted by Laroza and

Yabut (2020), technology can be used to deliver personalized instruction, which can help students learn at their own pace and in a way that suits their learning style. This can help students become more engaged in the learning process and, ultimately, improve their academic performance. Another advantage of technology integration is that it can help teachers save time and increase efficiency. According to Dimaunahan (2019), technology can be used to automate administrative tasks, such as attendance tracking and grading. This can help teachers focus more on teaching and less on administrative tasks, improving their overall effectiveness as educators. However, integrating technology into the classroom also presents challenges. One of the most significant challenges is the cost of technology and the associated infrastructure. As noted by Serrano and Tagulao (2020), the cost of technology can be a significant barrier for many schools in the Philippines, particularly those in

rural areas. To overcome this challenge, it is essential to allocate adequate resources to PFM and explore alternative funding sources.

3.5. *Physical Facilities Management*—Table 5 presents a summary of the extent of physical facilities management. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Technology Integration (3.14), Supporting People (3.11), and Establishing Process (2.16) are sometimes observed, while Facilities Upkeep and Improve (2.14) are rarely manifested. The overall mean score of 2.64 denotes that the extent of physical facilities management is moderately extensive in Tagum District Schools. Physical Facilities Management is a vital component of any educational institution, and the Philippine School System is no exception. The management of physical facilities is essential for the smooth functioning of a school and its ability to provide quality education.

Table 5. Summary of the Extent of Physical Facilities Management

No	Physical Facilities Management	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Supporting People	3.11	Moderately Extensive
2	Establishing Process	2.16	Less Extensive
3	Facilities Upkeep and Improve	2.16	Less Extensive
4	Technology Integration	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		2.64	Moderately Extensive

Supporting people is one of the essential components of physical facilities management in the Philippine School System. The management of physical facilities must consider the needs of the people who use them. According to Caraan (2021), it is crucial to have a dedicated team of maintenance staff who can ensure that the facilities are safe and clean. The staff must be adequately trained and equipped with the necessary tools and equipment to carry out their duties effectively. Furthermore, it is essential to provide ongoing training and support

to the staff to ensure that they are up-to-date with the latest technology and best practices. Establishing processes is another vital component of physical facilities management in the Philippine School System. According to Saez, Fernandez, and Morel (2021), it is essential to have a clear process in place for the management of physical facilities. This process should include regular inspections, maintenance, and repairs. Additionally, there should be a system in place for reporting any issues or concerns to the management team promptly. This will

ensure that any problems are addressed quickly, minimizing disruption to the school's daily operations. Facilities upkeep and improvement is another critical component of physical facilities management in the Philippine School System. According to Castillo (2020), it is essential to have a maintenance plan in place to ensure that the facilities are kept in good condition. This plan should include regular cleaning, repair, and replacement of equipment and fixtures. Additionally, there should be a budget set aside for the upkeep and improvement of the facilities. This will ensure that the school's physical facilities are always in top condition, providing a safe and comfortable learning environment for the students. Technology integration is another essential component of physical facilities management in the Philippine School System. According to Lapeña and De Leon (2019), technology can be used to improve the management of physical facilities. For example, a computerized maintenance management system (CMMS) can be used to track maintenance activities and manage work orders. Additionally, the integration of technology can help to improve energy efficiency and reduce costs. For instance, energy-efficient lighting and HVAC systems can be installed, and smart building technologies can be used to monitor and control energy usage.

3.6. Extent of School Safety—School safety is important for several reasons. According to Barrios, Garingan, and Jimenez (2019), school safety affects the physical and emotional well-being of students, teachers, and staff. When schools are unsafe, it can lead to anxiety, stress, and trauma for those involved. School safety is also important for the smooth running of a school. When students and teachers feel safe, they can focus on learning and teaching, respectively, and this can lead to better academic outcomes. Several measures can be taken to ensure school safety. According to Dizon, Encinares, and Rana (2020), these measures in-

clude the implementation of security protocols, the installation of security equipment, and the creation of a culture of safety. Security protocols can include measures such as identification checks, visitor sign-ins, and bag inspections. The installation of security equipment such as CCTV cameras and metal detectors can also help to improve school safety. Finally, creating a culture of safety involves promoting respect, responsibility, and positive behavior among students, teachers, and staff. Barrios, Garingan, and Jimenez (2019) conducted a study on the implementation of school safety programs in public schools in the Philippines. The study found that while there were some programs in place, they were not always effective. The authors recommended the creation of a more comprehensive and evidence-based school safety program. Dizon, Encinares, and Rana (2020) conducted a study on the implementation of school safety measures in the Philippines. The study found that while some schools had implemented security protocols and equipment, they were not always being used effectively. The authors recommended the need for more training and support for school staff in the implementation of these measures. School safety is a critical aspect of education that should not be ignored. It is important for the physical and emotional well-being of students, teachers, and staff and also for the smooth running of a school. Various measures can be taken to ensure school safety, including the implementation of security protocols, the installation of security equipment, and the creation of a culture of safety. By prioritizing school safety, we can create a safer and more conducive learning environment for all students.

3.7. Buildings and Classrooms—Indicated in Table 6 is the extent of school safety in terms of buildings and classrooms. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: the presence of ventilation and lighting (3.19); hallways and

pathways are safe (3.15); chalkboards are regularly cleaned up and dusts-free (3.15); clean classrooms and hazard-free floors (3.14); and chairs and desks are clean and safe (3.15), suggest the extent of school safety in terms of build-

ings and classrooms is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.15 denotes moderately extensive school safety in terms of buildings and classrooms.

Table 6. The Extent of School Safety in Terms of Buildings and Classrooms

No	Buildings and Classrooms	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Presence of ventilation and lighting	3.19	Moderately Extensive
2	Clean classrooms and hazard-free floors	3.14	Moderately Extensive
3	Hallways and pathways are safe	3.15	Moderately Extensive
4	Chairs and desks are clean and safe	3.14	Moderately Extensive
5	Chalkboards are regularly cleaned up and dust-free	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.15	Moderately Extensive

Buildings and classrooms play an essential role in school safety. According to Matuan and Canto (2019), school buildings and classrooms should be designed and constructed in a way that maximizes safety and security. This includes features such as appropriate lighting, ventilation, and emergency exits. Buildings and classrooms should also be designed with accessibility in mind to ensure that all students, including those with disabilities, can navigate them safely. In addition to design and construction, the maintenance of buildings and classrooms is also critical for school safety. According to Arizala et al. (2020), regular inspections and repairs can help to identify and address potential safety hazards, such as damaged flooring or faulty electrical wiring. This can prevent accidents and injuries from occurring. Matuan and Canto (2019) conducted a study on the de-

sign and construction of school buildings in the Philippines. The study found that while some schools had implemented safety features, others were lacking in this regard. The authors recommended the need for more comprehensive guidelines and standards for school building design and construction. Arizala et al. (2020) conducted a study on the maintenance of school buildings in the Philippines. The study found that while some schools had maintenance programs in place, they were not always being implemented effectively. The authors recommended the need for more training and support for school staff in the maintenance of buildings. Hidalgo et al. (2021) conducted a study on classroom management practices in the Philippines. The study found that certain classroom management practices, such as using visual aids, could help to create a safer classroom environment.

The authors recommended the need for more training and support for teachers in these practices. Finally, the use of classrooms can also impact school safety. According to Hidalgo et al. (2021), classroom management practices such as the arrangement of desks and the use of visual aids can impact student behavior and, therefore, contribute to a safer classroom environment. Teachers should also be trained to recognize and address potential safety issues, such as bullying or substance use.

3.8. *Water and Sanitation*—Indicated in Table 7 is the extent of school safety in terms of water and sanitation. The result is focused on

the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: medical and dental equipment are available in school health section (3.18); hand towels, sanitary napkins and toilet papers and other toiletries are available (3.15); first aid kits are present in the classroom for necessary and emergency use (3.15); washing of hands is regularly done (3.14); and water purifier or clean drinking water is available (3.12); suggest extent of school safety in terms of water and sanitation is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.14 denotes moderately extensive school safety in terms of water and sanitation.

Table 7. The Extent of School Safety in Terms of Water and Sanitation

No	Water and Sanitation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Water purifier or clean drinking water is available	3.12	Moderately Extensive
2	Washing of hands is regularly done	3.14	Moderately Extensive
3	Hand towels, sanitary napkins, toilet papers, and other toiletries are available	3.15	Moderately Extensive
4	Medical and dental equipment are available in the school health section	3.18	Moderately Extensive
5	First aid kits are present in the classroom for necessary and emergency use	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.14	Moderately Extensive

Access to clean water and adequate sanitation facilities is essential for ensuring a healthy and safe learning environment. According to Gonzales et al. (2020), the lack of clean water and sanitation facilities in schools can lead to the spread of waterborne diseases, such as diarrhea, which can affect students' attendance and academic performance. In addition to health concerns, the lack of water and sanitation facilities can also affect students' safety. Ac-

ording to Plata (2019), students, particularly girls, may be at risk of sexual assault when they have to travel outside the school to access sanitation facilities. This can lead to a decrease in attendance and poor academic performance. Therefore, ensuring access to clean water and adequate sanitation facilities within schools is crucial for promoting a safe and healthy learning environment. According to Gabrillo et al. (2021), implementing appropriate water and

sanitation facilities in schools can help to reduce absenteeism and improve academic performance. Gonzales et al. (2020) conducted a study on the availability of water and sanitation facilities in public schools in the Philippines. The study found that while most schools had access to water, sanitation facilities were lacking, particularly in rural areas. The authors recommended the need for more investment in sanitation facilities in schools. Plata (2019) conducted a study on the impact of sanitation facilities on the safety and well-being of female students in the Philippines. The study found that the lack of appropriate sanitation facilities in schools put female students at risk of sexual assault. The author recommended the need for more investment in appropriate sanitation facilities within schools. Gabriello et al. (2021) conducted a study on the impact of water and sanitation facilities on student attendance and academic performance in the Philippines. The study found that the availability of appropriate water and sanitation

facilities within schools was positively associated with student attendance and academic performance. The authors recommended the need for more investment in water and sanitation facilities in schools.

3.9. *Playground and Parking Spaces*—Indicated in Table 8 is the extent of school safety in terms of playground and parking spaces. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: parking space is supervised by school guards (3.18); enough space for learners to roam around for physical activities (3.15); bins are present in designated areas for waste management (3.15); hazard-free playing areas (3.14); and clean playing area (3.12), suggest extent of school safety in terms of playground and parking spaces are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.14 denotes moderately extensive school safety in terms of playground and parking spaces.

Table 8. The Extent of School Safety in Terms of Playground and Parking Spaces

No	Playground and Parking Spaces	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Clean playing area	3.12	Moderately Extensive
2	Hazard-free playing areas	3.14	Moderately Extensive
3	Enough space for learners to roam around for physical activities	3.15	Moderately Extensive
4	Parking space is supervised by school guards	3.18	Moderately Extensive
5	Bins are present in designated areas for waste management	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.14	Moderately Extensive

Playgrounds are an essential part of school safety as they provide students with an oppor-

tunity to engage in physical activity, which is crucial for their overall health and well-being.

However, playgrounds can also pose a risk of injury if they are not designed or maintained properly. According to Sharma and Prakash (2019), playgrounds should be designed with safety in mind, with appropriate equipment and surfaces to reduce the risk of injury. Similarly, parking spaces are essential for ensuring the safe and organized flow of traffic around schools. Inadequate parking spaces can lead to traffic congestion, which can pose a risk to both pedestrians and motorists. According to Ma et al. (2021), the design and management of parking spaces should prioritize safety, with appropriate signage, lighting, and traffic flow patterns to reduce the risk of accidents. Therefore, proper design and maintenance of playgrounds and parking spaces are crucial for promoting a safe and healthy learning environment. According to Mishra and Roy (2022), a well-designed and maintained playground and parking space can help to reduce the risk of accidents and promote safe and healthy physical activity among students. Sharma and Prakash (2019) conducted a study on the design and safety of playgrounds in schools in India. The study found that playgrounds in most schools did not meet safety guidelines and recommended the need for more

investment in playground design and maintenance. Ma et al. (2021) conducted a study on the design and management of parking spaces around schools in China. The study found that inadequate parking spaces and poor traffic management posed a risk to both pedestrians and motorists. The authors recommended the need for more investment in parking space design and management to promote safety. Mishra and Roy (2022) conducted a study on the role of playgrounds and parking spaces in promoting school safety in India. The study found that well-designed and maintained playgrounds and parking spaces can help to reduce the risk of accidents and promote safe and healthy physical activity among students. The authors recommended the need for more investment in playground and parking space design and maintenance.

3.10. *Extent of School Safety*—Table 9 presents a summary of the extent of school safety. This is presented in terms of highest to lowest mean scores: Water and Sanitation (3.15); Buildings and Classrooms (3.14); and Playground and Parking Spaces (3.14), suggesting the extent of school safety is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 9. Summary of the Extent of School Safety

No	School Safety	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Buildings and Classrooms	3.14	Moderately Extensive
2	Water and Sanitation	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	Playground and Parking Spaces	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.14	Moderately Extensive

Buildings and classrooms are crucial components of school safety. The safety of students in schools can be compromised by inadequate infrastructure, such as poorly constructed buildings and poorly maintained classrooms. According to a study by Kaur and Gupta (2019), the safety of students in schools is dependent

on the design and construction of school buildings. They argue that school buildings should be designed and constructed in such a way that they are earthquake-resistant, fire-resistant, and able to withstand other natural disasters. Water and sanitation are also essential components of school safety. A lack of safe and clean water and

sanitation facilities in schools can lead to the spread of waterborne diseases and other health issues. According to a study by Do and Kim (2020), ensuring adequate water and sanitation facilities in schools is critical to the safety and well-being of students. They argue that schools should have adequate handwashing facilities, clean toilets, and safe drinking water to prevent the spread of diseases. Playgrounds and parking spaces are also critical components of school safety. Playgrounds provide students with a space to engage in physical activity, which is essential for their physical and mental well-being. Mishra and Roy (2022) argue that playgrounds can also help prevent accidents in schools by providing students with a safe place to play. Additionally, parking spaces around schools are important for ensuring the safety of students

who walk or cycle to school. Ma et al. (2021) argues that parking spaces around schools should be designed and managed in a way that ensures the safety of students and pedestrians.

3.11. *Relationship between Physical Facilities Management and School Safety*—It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between physical facilities management ($r=0.897$; $p<.001$) and school safety. Table 10 revealed the yielded results of the significant correlation between physical facilities management and school safety. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between physical facilities management and school safety must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 10. Significant Relationship between Physical Facilities Management and School Safety

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
School Safety	0.897	<0.001	Significant	Reject H0

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$

In the international context, there is a growing recognition of the need for PFM and school safety. A study by Zhang, Zhao, and Wei (2019) highlights the importance of PFM in promoting school safety in China. The study found that poor PFM practices, such as inadequate ventilation and lighting, can compromise the safety and health of students. Therefore, the authors recommend that schools invest in PFM to ensure that their facilities meet the required safety standards. Similarly, in the Philippine context, PFM and school safety are critical components of the education system. According to the Department of Education (DepEd), PFM is essential in providing students with safe and comfortable learning spaces (DepEd, 2019). The DepEd has

implemented various measures to improve PFM in schools, such as providing guidelines for the design and construction of school buildings and facilities. Regarding school safety, the Philippine government has taken significant steps to ensure that schools are safe for students. In 2020, the DepEd issued guidelines for the safe reopening of schools during the COVID-19 pandemic (DepEd, 2020). The guidelines include measures such as regular disinfection of classrooms, installation of hand sanitizing stations, and physical distancing protocols. Furthermore, school safety also includes measures to ensure that students are safe from physical harm. A study by Rauf, Memon, and Chandio (2021) found that playgrounds are potential sites for ac-

cidents and injuries among students in Pakistan. The authors recommend that schools implement measures such as regular maintenance and inspection of playground equipment to ensure that they are safe for use.

3.12. *Domains of Physical Facilities Management that Significantly Influenced School Safety*—Table 11 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of physi-

cal facilities management that significantly influence school safety. All indicators of physical facilities management, including supporting people (0.002), establishing process (0.001), facilities upkeep and improvement (0.001), and technology integration (0.003), indicate a statistically significant influence on school safety. This shows that physical facilities management significantly influences school safety.

Table 11. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Physical Facilities Management Significantly Influencing School Safety

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.397		0.062	< .001	
H (Intercept)	0.401		0.144	0.006	
Supporting People	0.032	-0.021	0.066	0.002	Reject H0
Establishing Process	0.342	0.361	0.084	0.001	Reject H0
Facilities Upkeep and Improvement	0.207	0.215	0.094	0.001	Reject H0
Technology Integration	0.568	0.415	0.089	0.003	Reject H0

R² = 0.869
F-value = 225.896
p-value = <0.002

Note: *Significant at p < 0.05

Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.869 suggests that the indicators of physical facilities management explained 86.9%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (225.896) and F-statistic are significant p<.002, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of school safety. Physical Facilities Management (PFM) plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety and security of students and staff in educational institutions. In both international and Philippine settings, PFM must be given priority as it can significantly influence school safety. In the international setting, PFM practices such as regular inspection, maintenance, and repair of school buildings and facilities are crucial in ensuring school safety.

According to a study by Abdelhameed et al. (2020), routine inspection and maintenance of school buildings and facilities can help identify potential hazards and prevent accidents. In addition, the study recommends that schools should have an emergency management plan that includes regular safety drills to prepare students and staff for emergencies. Another PFM practice that can significantly influence school safety is the implementation of appropriate sanitation and hygiene measures. A study by Olu-dayo et al. (2021) emphasizes the importance of providing adequate and functional toilet facilities in schools to prevent the spread of diseases. The study also recommends the provision of handwashing facilities and the promotion of proper hygiene practices among students and

staff. In the Philippine setting, PFM practices such as providing safe drinking water and maintaining playgrounds and parking spaces are crucial in ensuring school safety. According to a study by Enemchukwu et al. (2020), providing safe drinking water in schools can prevent the spread of water-borne diseases. The study also recommends the implementation of regular cleaning and disinfection of drinking water storage tanks. Meanwhile, playground and parking space maintenance is also essential in ensuring school safety. A study by Bayot and Abasolo (2021) highlights the need for regular inspection and repair of playground equipment to prevent accidents. The study also recommends implementing traffic management policies to ensure the safety of students and staff in parking areas. In conclusion, PFM plays a significant role in ensuring school safety in both international and Philippine settings. Regular inspection and maintenance of school buildings and facilities, appropriate sanitation and hygiene measures, provision of safe drinking water, and maintenance of playgrounds and parking spaces are some of the PFM practices that significantly influence school safety. Educational institutions must prioritize PFM to ensure the safety and security of their students and staff.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and implications drawn. Findings were based on the problem's posed statement; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of physical facilities management in terms of technology integration (3.14) and supporting people (3.11) is sometimes observed while establishing processes (2.16) and facilities upkeep and improvement (2.14) are rarely manifested. The overall mean score of 2.64 denotes that the extent of physical facilities management was moderately extensive in Tagum District Schools. The extent of school safety in terms of water and sanitation (3.15), buildings and classrooms (3.14), and playground and parking spaces (3.14) suggests that it was sometimes manifested and thus moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between physical facilities management ($r=0.897$; $p<.001$) and school safety. All indicators of physical facilities management in terms of supporting people (0.002); establishing process (0.001); facilities upkeep and improvement (0.001); technology integration (0.003) indicate a statistically significant influence on school safety.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions, to wit; The extent of physical facilities management in terms of technology integration, supporting people, establishing processes, and facilities upkeep and improvement were moderately extensive in Tagum District Schools. The extent of school safety in terms of water and sanitation, buildings and classrooms, and playground and parking spaces suggest the extent of school safety is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive in Tagum District Schools. There was a significant correlation between physical facilities management and school safety in Tagum District Schools. All indicators of physical facilities management in terms of supporting people, establishing processes, facilities upkeep and improvement, and technology integration significantly influence

school safety in Tagum District Schools.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations to wit; Public School District Supervisor may develop and implement policies and procedures prioritizing the safety and security of school buildings, classrooms, water and sanitation facilities, playgrounds, and parking spaces. Regularly conduct safety audits and assessments to identify potential hazards and risks in school facilities. Allocate resources and funds to maintain and upgrade school facilities, especially those crucial to school safety. Provide training and professional development opportunities to school staff on safety protocols and emergency response procedures. Collaborate with local government agencies and community organizations to promote school safety and security. School Principals may establish a safety committee that includes teachers, staff, and parents to develop and implement safety protocols and emergency response procedures. Regularly conduct safety drills and exercises to ensure that all staff and students are familiar with safety procedures. Maintain open communication with the Public School District Supervisor and local government agencies to stay updated on the latest safety and security practices.

Ensure that all school staff are trained on safety protocols and emergency response procedures. Allocate resources and funds to maintain and upgrade school facilities, especially those crucial to school safety. Teachers should be familiar with safety protocols and emergency response procedures. They may regularly conduct safety drills and exercises to ensure all students are familiar with safety procedures. They may report any safety hazards or concerns to the School Principal or Public School District Supervisor. They may be vigilant and aware of potential safety risks in the classroom and school environment. They may also encourage students to report any safety concerns or incidents. For Future Research, they may conduct more research on the relationship between school safety and student academic achievement. Investigate the effectiveness of different safety protocols and emergency response procedures in school settings. Examine the impact of environmental factors, such as air quality and lighting, on school safety and well-being. Explore the role of technology in enhancing school safety and security. Study the impact of school safety policies and practices on teacher retention and job satisfaction.

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